

DIAGNOSTIC VALUE OF CLINICAL AND INSTRUMENTAL METHODS (MSCT) FOR DIFFERENT LOCALIZATION OF THE ORBITAL WALL FRACTURE

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The urgency of the problem. In recent years, as a result of an increase in the number of man-made disasters, criminal showdowns and road traffic accidents (RTA), the number of people injured with midface injuries has increased. Orbital fractures are one of the most common midface injuries, second only to those of the nasal bones. According to P. Siritongtaworn et al (2001), orbital fractures account for 40% of all fractures of the facial skeleton. Three quarters of the victims are men. Isolated orbital fractures occur in about 35–40% of cases; in 30–33% of victims, two walls are damaged. Fracture of three walls of the orbit is recorded in 15–20% of patients and in all four - in 5–10% of cases.

Under external influences on the orbit, mechanical injuries occur, accompanied by damage to soft tissues and bone structures. Small changes in the bone orbit, extraocular muscles, orbital tissue cause diplopia, decreased visual acuity, cosmetic defect, problems in the social and professional adaptation of the patient. In this regard, it is urgent to improve the quality of diagnostics in case of a fracture of the orbital wall.

Purpose of the study. Determine the diagnostic value of clinical and instrumental diagnostic methods for different localization of the orbital wall fracture.

Material and methods. We examined and inpatient treatment of 39 victims with damage and fractures of the orbit, who were treated in the emergency neurosurgery departments of the Fergana branch of the Republican Scientific Center for Emergency Medical Aid for the period 2018-2021. The age of the patients ranged from 4 to 63 years, of which 33 were men (84.6%) and 6 were women (15.3%).

Results and discussion. The causes of orbital trauma in 26 (66.6%) cases were road traffic accidents, in 4 (10.2%) criminal trauma, in 9 (23%) cases - domestic injury. Anamnesis was studied in all patients, a comprehensive ophthalmological examination was performed: visometry (with optimal correction), refractometry, biomicroscopy, ophthalmoscopy, tonometry, perimetry. The position of the eyeball was also determined using a Gertl mirror exophthalmometer. Examination of the patients revealed clinical symptoms: tense eyelid hematoma - 37 (94.8%) patients, limitation of eyeball mobility - 11 (28.2%), diplopia - 4 (10.2%). On palpation of the inferior orbital edge, pain was identified, the symptom of a "step" - 4 (10.2%), crepitus of the eyelid skin - 5 (12.8%). In 2 (5.1%) patients, orbital trauma was combined with severe eyeball contusion: retinal detachment - 1 (2.5%), penetrating eye injury with prolapse of the vitreous body and iris 1 (2.5%). All the victims underwent MSCT at once according to the algorithm developed by

us. Multispiral computed tomography (MSCT) is the gold standard in the diagnosis of orbital fractures, allowing you to accurately reproduce the appearance of the orbital skeleton and adjacent structures in several planes. 3D reconstruction provides reliable information about the number of orbital bone fragments and their position. MSCT eliminates the need for radiography, thereby reducing radiation exposure and economic costs, shortening the diagnosis time in emergency situations. The nature of TBI was determined on the basis of clinical and instrumental diagnostic methods: Concussion was detected in 21 (53.8%) patients. Brain contusions were found in 18 (46.1%), with a predominant lesion of the frontal lobes - in 7 (17.9%). The results after MSCT-studies, depending on the localization of damage to the walls of the orbit, we identified the following groups: nasoorbital (NOE) fractures 5 (12.8%), fractures of the zygomatic-orbital complex 6 (15.3%), fractures of the upper jaw-lower orbital wall 4 (10.2%), frontal basal fractures 7 (17.9%), upper lateral wall 4 (10.2%), combined fractures 13 (33.3%). Damage to the right eye was diagnosed in 21 (53.8%), left eye 18 (46.1%). In one case, the cause of the car accident was a fracture of the orbit of both eyes. Fractures of the walls of the orbit, which required reconstructive and restorative treatment, were diagnosed in 11 (28.2%) patients with a mixed fracture of the orbital walls. In 13 (33.3%) patients, injuries to the lateral, medial and inferior orbital walls were observed, accompanied by severe deformation of the orbit, dislocation of adipose tissue and oculomotor muscles in the fracture gap, and development of strabismus. Isolated injuries of the lower wall of the orbit were diagnosed in 4 (10.2%) cases.

All patients in the preoperative period had deformity of the orbit, oculomotor disorders in the form of limited mobility of the eyeball and diplopia of various nature. Fracture with mixing of the walls of the orbit 11 and the operation was performed resection trepanation, removal of depressed bone fragments from the upper wall of the orbit 4 (10.2%).

Conclusions. An operation to remove compressive bone fragments in the early period of orbital trauma allows achieving regression of oculomotor disorders 85%, eyeball dystopia 80%, diplopia 84%, and good cosmetic outcomes.

In conclusion, we can say that timely topical diagnostics and qualified assistance provided for orbital injuries prevent serious consequences and preserve the patient's eyesight